

Database of Research Infrastructure User Training Requirements

OGS, National Institute of Oceanography and Applied
Geophysics

Andrea Caburlotto

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About this document

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1. Executive Summary

AQUARIUS is a Horizon Europe funded project that runs from March 1, 2024, to the end of February 2028. Its overarching aim is to provide a highly comprehensive suite of integrated research infrastructures designed to address significant challenges for the long-term sustainability of our unique oceans, seas, and freshwater ecosystems. An impressive range of 57 research infrastructure services will be made available through Transnational Access (TA) Calls, including research vessels, mobile marine observation platforms, fixed marine facilities, experimental research facilities, river & basin supersites, aircraft, drones, satellite services, and sophisticated data infrastructures.

The approach and activities planned under the "Research Infrastructure (RI) Technical Training" programme aim to ensure the achievement of AQUARIUS objective 5, to ensure personalised and highly efficient training and scientific and technical support to users of research infrastructures.

The aim is therefore to identify training needs and gaps that can be addressed to ensure that the research infrastructures (RIs) offered by the AQUARIUS project can be used appropriately and efficiently to maximise the benefits for researchers and their projects.

A questionnaire on RI technical training was prepared and sent to each RI operator to obtain information on the need for specific and/or the possibility of organising specific training if requested by users, and on any material (videos, presentations, manuals, etc.) that can provide further information on the potentiality and data that can be obtained from the infrastructure.

This document outlines the process and steps taken to create the Database of Research Infrastructure User Training Requirements. All training materials shared by RI operators will be accessible on the [AQUARIUS Training Hub](#).

2. Introduction

D5.1 is related to Task 5.1 of the DoA, which is:

"Training Needs Analysis & Ad hoc Training for RI Users (RV, Fixed & Mobile Platforms)"

The Training Needs Analysis will be conducted prior to the development of any training, through surveys of each of the RI providers. Training is likely to be required across multiple infrastructures, therefore customized programs will be developed. Technical training will cover the selected RIs, which could include, for instance, a combination of research vessels, remotely operated (as well as autonomous) underwater vehicles, aircraft, gliders, drones, sensors, fixed platforms, experimental facilities, and sophisticated data infrastructures. It is intended that most of the training will be done on-site where necessary, but also online and made available for reuse. Shared training across multiple projects using the same infrastructure will be facilitated, to optimize and make efficient use of the resources.

These objectives will be achieved by:

- Conducting a survey of all Research Infrastructure training requirements for access to infrastructure
- Producing a database of all training access requirements in advance of TA call publication
- Ad hoc training will be provided by infrastructures on-site where necessary and or online and made available for reuse via the AQUARIUS Technical Training Hub (Task 5.3).
- Organizing shared training across multiple projects using the same infrastructure, to optimize and make efficient use of the resources.

- In the event of training being required across multiple applications, the project will arrange for an integrated course to be conducted.

3. Method and Results

3.1. RI Technical Training survey

To develop the AQUARIUS RI Technical Training database, firstly each of the Research Infrastructures were organized by the 8 RI types adopted in the AQUARIUS Infrastructure Catalogue, that are:

- Research Vessels
- Marine Mobile Observation Platforms
- Fixed Marine Facilities
- Experimental Research Facilities
- River & Basin Supersites
- Aircraft
- Drones
- Satellite Services

A survey was prepared and circulated to identify any training needs and gap analysis that can be addressed to ensure that the RI can be used appropriately and efficiently to maximise the benefit for the researchers and their projects.

The questionnaire ([Appendix 1](#)) contains 9 questions to the RI operators:

Q 1. Are Infrastructure Users required to undertake any training prior to accessing your infrastructure?

Q 2. Do you (Infrastructure Operator) provide the training or is it provided by an external organization? (if the answer to Q1 is YES)

Q 3. Do you organize the training for the Users or is it Users' responsibility to organize training? (if the answer to Q1 is YES)

Q 4. Is there training material available to ensure that the RI can be used appropriately and efficiently to maximise the benefit for the researchers and their projects?

Q 5. What kind of material is available online?

Q 6. Do you plan to provide any online training materials before the 1st TA call (November 2024) / or before end of JUNE?

Q 7. Are you willing to share available training material (if any) on the AQUARIUS Training Hub?

Q 8. Is on-site training necessary for TA users to utilize the RI?

Q 9. If requested by TA users, will you arrange on-site or on-line training course?

The survey was sent in MS Form format to all the AQUARIUS Infrastructure operators. To streamline the process and reduce the need for multiple outreach efforts, the decision was made to include the WP5 Training Questionnaire within the RI Profile Data Collection forms ([Deliverable 4.1](#)) which were subsequently used to populate the [Online Infrastructures Catalogue](#). This integration aimed to cover all necessary aspects without the need for repeated follow-ups.

Initially, response rates were slow, so the deadline (June 30th) was postponed to October 31st, after the summertime. The responses improved as the deadline approached. The data collected from the survey were organized in a database of all training access requirements and where prior training was necessary to access the RI this was shared in the Online Infrastructures Catalogue.

3.2. Results and comments

The database contains a total of 61 Research Infrastructures available in the AQUARIUS project.

The results of the survey were analysed based on the 8 RI types contained in the AQUARIUS infrastructure catalogue, whereby each infrastructure type was divided into two sub-areas:

- Training needs – to obtain information on the need for specific and/or the possibility of organising specific training if requested by users.
- Training material availability – acquire material from the RIs any material (videos, presentations, manuals, etc.) that can provide further information on the potentiality and data that can be obtained from the infrastructure.

3.2.1. Research Vessels

Training Needs

Out of 18 Research Vessels(RVs) available in AQUARIUS, 11 do not require prior training before accessing the RI and 7 RVs required users to receive training before accessing the RI: 4 of the latter provide the training, 2 provide the training through the RV operator in collaboration with external organisations and 1 should be provided by users, while in 1 RV the users have to organise the training themselves, 3 are organised by the RV operator and 3 will be organized by users in collaboration with the operators. Only 4 RVs require on-site training. 15 out of 18 RV operators will organise on-site or online training at the request of TA users.

<p>IS ON-SITE TRAINING NECESSARY FOR TA USERS TO UTILIZE THE RI?</p>		
YES	4	
NO	14	
N/A	0	
<p>IF REQUESTED BY TA USERS, WILL YOU ARRANGE ON-SITE OR ON-LINE TRAINING COURSE?</p>		
YES	15	
NO	2	
N/A	1	

Training material availability

Only 4 RV operators have training material available, and 5 plan to provide online training material by November 2024.

13 of the RV Operators are willing to share available training material on the online [AQUARIUS Training Hub](#).

TRAINING MATERIAL AVAILABILITY		
<p>IS THERE TRAINING MATERIAL AVAILABLE TO ENSURE THAT THE RI CAN BE USED APPROPRIATELY AND EFFICIENTLY TO MAXIMISE THE BENEFIT FOR THE RESEARCHERS AND THEIR PROJECTS?</p>		
YES	4	
NO	14	
N/A	0	
<p>DO YOU PLAN TO PROVIDE ANY ONLINE TRAINING MATERIALS BEFORE THE 1ST TA CALL (NOVEMBER 2024)</p>		
YES	5	
NO	13	
N/A	0	
<p>ARE YOU WILLING TO SHARE AVAILABLE TRAINING MATERIAL (IF ANY) ON THE AQUARIUS TRAINING HUB?</p>		
YES	13	
NO	3	
N/A	2	

3.2.2. Mobile Marine Observatory Platforms

Training Needs

Out of 13 Mobile Marine Observatory Platforms available, 6 do not require prior training before accessing the RI and 7 required users to receive training before accessing the RI: all the RI operators of the latter will provide and organize the training. Only 3 infrastructures require on-site training, and 12 RV operators will organise on-site or online training at the request of TA users.

TRAINING NEEDS													
<p>ARE INFRASTRUCTURES USERS REQUIRED TO UNDERTAKE ANY TRAINING PRIOR TO ACCESSING YOUR INFRASTRUCTURE?</p> <p>YES 7</p> <p>NO 6</p> <p>N/A 0</p>	<table border="1"> <caption>Training Requirements</caption> <thead> <tr> <th>Response</th> <th>Count</th> <th>Percentage</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>YES</td> <td>7</td> <td>54%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>NO</td> <td>6</td> <td>46%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>N/A</td> <td>0</td> <td>0%</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Response	Count	Percentage	YES	7	54%	NO	6	46%	N/A	0	0%
Response	Count	Percentage											
YES	7	54%											
NO	6	46%											
N/A	0	0%											
<p>DO YOU (INFRASTRUCTURE OPERATOR) PROVIDE THE TRAINING OR IS IT PROVIDED BY AN EXTERNAL ORGANIZATION? <i>(if answered YES in Q1)</i></p> <p>RI OPERATOR 7</p> <p>EXTERNAL ORGANIZATION 0</p> <p>BOTH 0</p>	<table border="1"> <caption>Training Provider</caption> <thead> <tr> <th>Provider</th> <th>Count</th> <th>Percentage</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>RI Operator</td> <td>7</td> <td>100%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>External organization</td> <td>0</td> <td>0%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Both</td> <td>0</td> <td>0%</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Provider	Count	Percentage	RI Operator	7	100%	External organization	0	0%	Both	0	0%
Provider	Count	Percentage											
RI Operator	7	100%											
External organization	0	0%											
Both	0	0%											
<p>DO YOU ORGANIZE THE TRAINING FOR THE USERS OR IS IT USERS' RESPONSIBILITY TO ORGANIZE TRAINING? <i>(if answered YES in Q1)</i></p> <p>RI OPERATOR 7</p> <p>USERS 0</p> <p>BOTH 0</p>	<table border="1"> <caption>Training Organization</caption> <thead> <tr> <th>Organizer</th> <th>Count</th> <th>Percentage</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>RI Operator</td> <td>7</td> <td>100%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>External organization</td> <td>0</td> <td>0%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Both</td> <td>0</td> <td>0%</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Organizer	Count	Percentage	RI Operator	7	100%	External organization	0	0%	Both	0	0%
Organizer	Count	Percentage											
RI Operator	7	100%											
External organization	0	0%											
Both	0	0%											
<p>IS ON-SITE TRAINING NECESSARY FOR TA USERS TO UTILIZE THE RI?</p> <p>YES 3</p> <p>NO 10</p> <p>N/A 0</p>	<table border="1"> <caption>On-site Training Necessity</caption> <thead> <tr> <th>Response</th> <th>Count</th> <th>Percentage</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>YES</td> <td>3</td> <td>23%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>NO</td> <td>10</td> <td>77%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>N/A</td> <td>0</td> <td>0%</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Response	Count	Percentage	YES	3	23%	NO	10	77%	N/A	0	0%
Response	Count	Percentage											
YES	3	23%											
NO	10	77%											
N/A	0	0%											
<p>IF REQUESTED BY TA USERS, WILL YOU ARRANGE ON-SITE OR ON-LINE TRAINING COURSE?</p> <p>YES 12</p> <p>NO 1</p> <p>N/A 0</p>	<table border="1"> <caption>Training Arrangement</caption> <thead> <tr> <th>Response</th> <th>Count</th> <th>Percentage</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>YES</td> <td>12</td> <td>92%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>NO</td> <td>1</td> <td>8%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>N/A</td> <td>0</td> <td>0%</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Response	Count	Percentage	YES	12	92%	NO	1	8%	N/A	0	0%
Response	Count	Percentage											
YES	12	92%											
NO	1	8%											
N/A	0	0%											

Training material availability

8 RI operators have training material available, whereas none of the operators plan to provide online training material by November 2024.

9 of the Mobile Marine Observatory operators are willing to share available training material on the AQUARIUS Training Hub.

3.2.3. Fixed Marine Facilities

Training Needs

Out of 11 Fixed Marine Facilities available, 9 do not require users to undertake training before accessing the RI, 1 did not respond, and 1 required users to receive training before accessing the RI and will provide and organize the training through the RV operator. 9 platforms require on-site training (2 didn't give feedback). 10 out of 11 operators will organise on-site or online training if requested by TA users (1 didn't answer).

<p>DO YOU (INFRASTRUCTURE OPERATOR) <u>PROVIDE</u> THE TRAINING OR IS IT PROVIDED BY AN EXTERNAL ORGANIZATION? <i>(if answered YES in Q1)</i></p> <p>RI OPERATOR 0 EXTERNAL ORGANIZATION 1 BOTH 0</p>	
<p>DO YOU <u>ORGANIZE</u> THE TRAINING FOR THE USERS OR IS IT USERS' RESPONSIBILITY TO ORGANIZE TRAINING? <i>(if answered YES in Q1)</i></p> <p>RI OPERATOR 0 USERS 1 BOTH 0</p>	
<p>IS ON-SITE TRAINING NECESSARY FOR TA USERS TO UTILIZE THE RI?</p> <p>YES 0 NO 9 N/A 2</p>	
<p>IF REQUESTED BY TA USERS, WILL YOU ARRANGE ON-SITE OR ON-LINE TRAINING COURSE?</p> <p>YES 10 NO 0 N/A 1</p>	

Training material availability

One RI operator has training material available, and 10 facilities do not plan to provide online training material by November 2024. Furthermore, 8 infrastructures are willing to share any available training material on the AQUARIUS Training Hub.

TRAINING MATERIAL AVAILABILITY	
<p>IS THERE TRAINING MATERIAL AVAILABLE TO ENSURE THAT THE RI CAN BE USED APPROPRIATELY AND EFFICIENTLY TO MAXIMISE THE BENEFIT FOR THE RESEARCHERS AND THEIR PROJECTS?</p> <p>YES 1 NO 9 N/A 1</p>	

DO YOU PLAN TO PROVIDE ANY ONLINE TRAINING MATERIALS BEFORE THE 1ST TA CALL (NOVEMBER 2024)		
YES	0	
NO	10	
N/A	1	
ARE YOU WILLING TO SHARE AVAILABLE TRAINING MATERIAL (IF ANY) ON THE AQUARIUS TRAINING HUB?		
YES	8	
NO	1	
N/A	2	

3.2.4. Experimental Research Facilities

Training Needs

Out of 9 Experimental Research Facilities available, 5 do not require prior training before accessing the RI and 4 required users to receive training before accessing the RI. 3 institutions requiring training will provide and organize the training, and 1 will provide the training through an external organization and the users must organize the training. 4 others are available to organize and provide the training for the use of certain equipment, whereas 1 of them will organise the training by an external organization. 4 operators require on-site training, and 3 out of 9 operators will organise on-site or online training if requested by TA users (1 didn't answer).

TRAINING NEEDS	
ARE INFRASTRUCTURES USERS REQUIRED TO UNDERTAKE ANY TRAINING PRIOR TO ACCESSING YOUR INFRASTRUCTURE?	
YES	4
NO	5
N/A	0
DO YOU (INFRASTRUCTURE OPERATOR) PROVIDE THE TRAINING OR IS IT PROVIDED BY AN EXTERNAL ORGANIZATION? <i>(if answered YES in Q1)</i>	
RI OPERATOR	5
EXTERNAL ORGANIZATION	1
BOTH	0

<p>DO YOU <u>ORGANIZE</u> THE TRAINING FOR THE USERS OR IS IT USERS' RESPONSIBILITY TO ORGANIZE TRAINING? <i>(if answered YES in Q1)</i></p>		
RI OPERATOR	6	
USERS	1	
BOTH	0	
<p>IS ON-SITE TRAINING NECESSARY FOR TA USERS TO UTILIZE THE RI?</p>		
YES	4	
NO	5	
N/A	2	
<p>IF REQUESTED BY TA USERS, WILL YOU ARRANGE ON-SITE OR ON-LINE TRAINING COURSE?</p>		
YES	3	
NO	6	
N/A	2	

Training material availability

Only 2 RI operators have training material available, and 1 facility will provide online training material by November 2024. Furthermore, 1 infrastructure is willing to share any available training material that may be produced on the AQUARIUS Training Hub.

TRAINING MATERIAL AVAILABILITY		
<p>IS THERE TRAINING MATERIAL AVAILABLE TO ENSURE THAT THE RI CAN BE USED APPROPRIATELY AND EFFICIENTLY TO MAXIMISE THE BENEFIT FOR THE RESEARCHERS AND THEIR PROJECTS?</p>		
YES	2	
NO	7	
N/A	0	
<p>DO YOU PLAN TO PROVIDE ANY ONLINE TRAINING MATERIALS BEFORE THE 1ST TA CALL (NOVEMBER 2024)</p>		
YES	1	
NO	8	
N/A	0	

3.2.5. River and Basin Supersites

Training Needs

Out of 4 supersites available, 3 of them require prior training before accessing the RI, 2 of them will provide and organize the training and 1 will provide the training in collaboration with external organisations. 2 infrastructures require on-site training, and 3 operators will organise on-site or online training if requested by TA users (1 didn't answer).

IF REQUESTED BY TA USERS, WILL YOU ARRANGE ON-SITE OR ON-LINE TRAINING COURSE?		
YES	3	
NO	0	
N/A	1	

Training material availability

2 RI operators have training material to ensure that the RI can be used appropriately and efficiently to maximise the benefits for researchers and their projects, and no facility can provide online training material currently. Furthermore, 3 infrastructures are willing to share available training material (if any) on the AQUARIUS Training Hub.

TRAINING MATERIAL AVAILABILITY		
IS THERE TRAINING MATERIAL AVAILABLE TO ENSURE THAT THE RI CAN BE USED APPROPRIATELY AND EFFICIENTLY TO MAXIMISE THE BENEFIT FOR THE RESEARCHERS AND THEIR PROJECTS?		
YES	2	
NO	2	
N/A	0	
DO YOU PLAN TO PROVIDE ANY ONLINE TRAINING MATERIALS BEFORE THE 1ST TA CALL (NOVEMBER 2024)		
YES	0	
NO	3	
N/A	1	
ARE YOU WILLING TO SHARE AVAILABLE TRAINING MATERIAL (IF ANY) ON THE AQUARIUS TRAINING HUB?		
YES	3	
NO	0	
N/A	1	

3.2.6. Aircraft

Training Needs

Out of 4 aircraft available, 2 of them require prior training before accessing the RI, and 1 of them provides the training through an external organisation and the users need to organize the training. 1 infrastructure requires on-site training, and 1 operator will organise on-site or online training if requested by TA users.

TRAINING NEEDS													
<p>ARE INFRASTRUCTURES USERS REQUIRED TO UNDERTAKE ANY TRAINING PRIOR TO ACCESSING YOUR INFRASTRUCTURE?</p> <p>YES 2</p> <p>NO 1</p> <p>N/A 0</p>	<table border="1"> <caption>Training Requirements</caption> <thead> <tr> <th>Response</th> <th>Count</th> <th>Percentage</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>YES</td> <td>2</td> <td>67%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>NO</td> <td>1</td> <td>33%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>N/A</td> <td>0</td> <td>0%</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Response	Count	Percentage	YES	2	67%	NO	1	33%	N/A	0	0%
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N/A	1	50%											
RI Operator	0	0%											
<p>DO YOU ORGANIZE THE TRAINING FOR THE USERS' RESPONSIBILITY TO ORGANIZE TRAINING? <i>(if answered YES in Q1)</i></p> <p>RI OPERATOR 1</p> <p>USERS 0</p> <p>BOTH 0</p>	<table border="1"> <caption>Training Organizer</caption> <thead> <tr> <th>Response</th> <th>Count</th> <th>Percentage</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>RI Operator</td> <td>1</td> <td>50%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>N/A</td> <td>1</td> <td>50%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Users</td> <td>0</td> <td>0%</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Response	Count	Percentage	RI Operator	1	50%	N/A	1	50%	Users	0	0%
Response	Count	Percentage											
RI Operator	1	50%											
N/A	1	50%											
Users	0	0%											
<p>IS ON-SITE TRAINING NECESSARY FOR TA USERS TO UTILIZE THE RI?</p> <p>YES 1</p> <p>NO 1</p> <p>N/A 1</p>	<table border="1"> <caption>On-site Training Necessity</caption> <thead> <tr> <th>Response</th> <th>Count</th> <th>Percentage</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>YES</td> <td>1</td> <td>34%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>N/A</td> <td>1</td> <td>33%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>NO</td> <td>1</td> <td>33%</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Response	Count	Percentage	YES	1	34%	N/A	1	33%	NO	1	33%
Response	Count	Percentage											
YES	1	34%											
N/A	1	33%											
NO	1	33%											
<p>IF REQUESTED BY TA USERS, WILL YOU ARRANGE ON-SITE OR ON-LINE TRAINING COURSE?</p> <p>YES 1</p> <p>NO 1</p> <p>N/A 1</p>	<table border="1"> <caption>Training Arrangement</caption> <thead> <tr> <th>Response</th> <th>Count</th> <th>Percentage</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>YES</td> <td>1</td> <td>34%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>N/A</td> <td>1</td> <td>33%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>NO</td> <td>1</td> <td>33%</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Response	Count	Percentage	YES	1	34%	N/A	1	33%	NO	1	33%
Response	Count	Percentage											
YES	1	34%											
N/A	1	33%											
NO	1	33%											

Training material availability

1 aircraft operator has training material available for users, and no facility can provide online training material currently for the AQUARIUS Training Hub.

3.2.7. Drones

Training Needs

The 2 Drones available require users to undergo training before accessing the RI, and both the research infrastructures operators will provide and organize the training. 1 infrastructure requires on-site training, and both operators will organise on-site or online training if requested by TA users.

<p>DO YOU (INFRASTRUCTURE OPERATOR) <u>PROVIDE</u> THE TRAINING OR IS IT PROVIDED BY AN EXTERNAL ORGANIZATION? <i>(if answered YES in Q1)</i></p> <p>RI OPERATOR 2 EXTERNAL ORGANIZATION 0 BOTH 0</p>	
<p>DO YOU <u>ORGANIZE</u> THE TRAINING FOR THE USERS OR IS IT USERS' RESPONSIBILITY TO ORGANIZE TRAINING? <i>(if answered YES in Q1)</i></p> <p>RI OPERATOR 2 USERS 0 BOTH 0</p>	
<p>IS ON-SITE TRAINING NECESSARY FOR TA USERS TO UTILIZE THE RI?</p> <p>YES 1 NO 1 N/A 0</p>	
<p>IF REQUESTED BY TA USERS, WILL YOU ARRANGE ON-SITE OR ON-LINE TRAINING COURSE?</p> <p>YES 2 NO 0 N/A 0</p>	

Training material availability

1 of the 2 Drone operators has training material available and will provide any online training material available for the AQUARIUS Training Hub.

TRAINING MATERIAL AVAILABILITY	
<p>IS THERE TRAINING MATERIAL AVAILABLE TO ENSURE THAT THE RI CAN BE USED APPROPRIATELY AND EFFICIENTLY TO MAXIMISE THE BENEFIT FOR THE RESEARCHERS AND THEIR PROJECTS?</p> <p>YES 1 NO 1 N/A 0</p>	

<p>DO YOU PLAN TO PROVIDE ANY ONLINE TRAINING MATERIALS BEFORE THE 1ST TA CALL (NOVEMBER 2024)</p> <p>YES 1</p> <p>NO 1</p> <p>N/A 0</p>	
<p>ARE YOU WILLING TO SHARE AVAILABLE TRAINING MATERIAL (IF ANY) ON THE AQUARIUS TRAINING HUB?</p> <p>YES 1</p> <p>NO 1</p> <p>N/A 0</p>	

3.2.8. Satellite Services

Training Needs

The Satellite Services Terrascope operator didn't provide any information about the requirement of prior training before accessing the RI; this infrastructure doesn't require on-site training but will organise on-site or online training if requested by TA users.

TRAINING NEEDS	
<p>ARE INFRASTRUCTURES USERS REQUIRED TO UNDERTAKE ANY TRAINING PRIOR TO ACCESSING YOUR INFRASTRUCTURE?</p> <p>YES 0</p> <p>NO 0</p> <p>N/A 1</p>	N/A
<p>DO YOU (INFRASTRUCTURE OPERATOR) <u>PROVIDE</u> THE TRAINING OR IS IT PROVIDED BY AN EXTERNAL ORGANIZATION?</p> <p><i>(if answered YES in Q1)</i></p> <p>RI OPERATOR 0</p> <p>EXTERNAL ORGANIZATION 0</p> <p>BOTH 0</p>	N/A
<p>DO YOU <u>ORGANIZE</u> THE TRAINING FOR THE USERS OR IS IT USERS' RESPONSIBILITY TO ORGANIZE TRAINING?</p> <p><i>(if answered YES in Q1)</i></p> <p>RI OPERATOR 0</p> <p>USERS 0</p> <p>BOTH 0</p>	N/A

IS ON-SITE TRAINING NECESSARY FOR TA USERS TO UTILIZE THE RI?		
YES	0	
NO	1	
N/A	0	
IF REQUESTED BY TA USERS, WILL YOU ARRANGE ON-SITE OR ON-LINE TRAINING COURSE?		
YES	1	
NO	0	
N/A	0	

Training material availability

Terrascope operator provided training material on the use of the infrastructure and shared the material in the AQUARIUS Training Hub.

TRAINING MATERIAL AVAILABILITY		
IS THERE TRAINING MATERIAL AVAILABLE TO ENSURE THAT THE RI CAN BE USED APPROPRIATELY AND EFFICIENTLY TO MAXIMISE THE BENEFIT FOR THE RESEARCHERS AND THEIR PROJECTS?		
YES	1	
NO	0	
N/A	0	
DO YOU PLAN TO PROVIDE ANY ONLINE TRAINING MATERIALS BEFORE THE 1ST TA CALL (NOVEMBER 2024)		
YES	1	
NO	0	
N/A	0	
ARE YOU WILLING TO SHARE AVAILABLE TRAINING MATERIAL (IF ANY) ON THE AQUARIUS TRAINING HUB?		
YES	1	
NO	0	
N/A	0	

4. In Conclusion

The AQUARIUS database “Research Infrastructures User Training Requirement” was developed to ensure the achievement of AQUARIUS Objective 5 and to ensure that customised and highly efficient training and scientific and technical support is provided to users of the research infrastructures. Where training is required prior to users accessing the infrastructures, this information was included in the relevant Infrastructure’s Profile Page in the [AQUARIUS Infrastructures Catalogue](#) to inform users in advance.

The ad hoc technical training for users of the AQUARIUS infrastructure services was based on a training needs and gaps analysis to ensure that the RI can be used appropriately and efficiently to maximise the benefits for researchers and their projects. The training needs analysis was conducted through surveys of all RI providers prior to the development of training courses. 61 RI operators completed the questionnaire, and their feedback was divided into two sub-areas:

Training needs

Regarding the Training needs, a good response was received from the RI operators. 26 RIs require the users to undertake training prior to accessing the infrastructure, and 18 of them will provide and organize the training courses, 4 will be provided by external organizations and 4 will be organized by the users. For 3 RIs, they will provide and organize the training in conjunction with external organizations and users. 24 RIs need on-site training for TA users, and 47 will arrange on-site or on-line training courses for the TA users if requested. There was no common training gap identified across multiple infrastructures as most training required is infrastructure specific and is either provided by the RI operators on an ad hoc basis or organised by them through external training providers as required.

Training material availability

Regarding the availability of RI training materials and sharing those resources (videos, presentations, manuals, etc) that can provide further information on the potentiality and data that can be obtained from the infrastructure, the feedback received is as below; 21 of 61 RI operators have training material available, and 9 plan to provide any online training. Moreover, 37 RI are willing to share training materials on the AQUARIUS Training Hub.

It is likely that some operators do not have training material available currently but may produce it later, this will be monitored and the database and AQUARIUS Training Hub updated as materials become available. 43 infrastructures provided educational posters of their infrastructure for AQUARIUS brokerage events prior to the first TA call opening and these are also available on the AQUARIUS Training Hub.

All training resources already available and those that will become available throughout the project lifetime will be shared on the [AQUARIUS Training Hub](#).

5. Appendices

5.1. Appendix 1 - RI Technical Training Survey RI operators

The purpose of this section is to identify any training needs and gap analysis that can be addressed to ensure that the RI can be used appropriately and efficiently to maximise the benefit for the researchers and their projects. A database of all training access requirements will be produced in line with the first Transnational Access call to inform users. All training resources will be shared via the *AQUARIUS Technical Training Hub* throughout the project.

Q 1. Are Infrastructure Users required to undertake any training prior to accessing your infrastructure?

- YES
- NO (Go to Q4)

If yes, please provide details

If yes, please provide details

Q 2. Do you (Infrastructure Operator) provide the training or is it provided by an external organization?

- Infrastructure Operator provides the training
- External Organization provides the training

Please provide details

Please provide details

Q 3. Do you organize the training for the Users or is it Users' responsibility to organize training?

- Infrastructure Operator organizes training
- Users organize training

Q 4. Is there training material available to ensure that the RI can be used appropriately and efficiently to maximise the benefit for the researchers and their projects?

- YES (go to Q5)
- NO (go to Q6)

Q 5. What kind of material is available online?

Webinar		
Workshop(s)		
Video		
Brochure		
Presentation (ppt, pdf)		
Other		

If you selected Other, please specify here.

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Q 6. Do you plan to provide any online training materials before the 1st TA call (November 2024) / or before of end JUNE?

- YES
- NO

If Yes, please provide details (when will the training materials be available?)

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Q 7. Are you willing to share available training material (if any) on the AQUARIUS Training Hub?

- YES
- NO

Q 8. Is on-site training necessary for TA users to utilize the RI?

- YES
- NO

Q 9. If requested by TA users, will you arrange on-site or on-line training course?

- YES
- NO

If YES, please provide details

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Q 10. Please confirm if you can host young scientists/technicians to complete Internships (during TA and/or non-TA activities, like i.e. periodic cruises, maintenance of RI, etc)?

- YES
- NO

If YES, please provide details (when, for how long, etc)

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5.2. Appendix 2 Results of Research Infrastructure Training Needs Survey

Name of Infrastructure:	Are Infrastructure Users required to undertake any training prior to accessing your infrastructure?	If yes, please provide details:
Research Vessels		
RV Celtic Explorer	No	
RV Svea	No	
RV Sanna	No	
RV Wim Wolff	No	
RV Belgica	No	
RV Simon Stevin	Yes	Depending on facilities used – e.g. CTD, multibeam,
RV Mare Nigrum	No	
RV Sarmiento de Gamboa	No	
RV Aranda	Yes	One day STCW Basic Safety Training or equivalent. Every scientific person must participate in the safety and laboratory training and familiarize oneself the Aranda manual, before every cruise.
RV Aegaeo	Yes	Safety training and introduction to the platform facilities during first visit
RV Socib	No	

Name of Infrastructure:	Are Infrastructure Users required to undertake any training prior to accessing your infrastructure?	If yes, please provide details:
RV Thalassa	No	
RV L'Europe	No	
RV G. O. Sars	Yes	Cruise leader needs to do a cruise leader course, one day, online.
RV Jákup Sverri	No	
RV Arni Fridriksson	Yes	STCW A-VI/1 by external trainer. Safety training for people coming onboard (given on the ship one hour before departure).
Gaia Blu	Yes	STCW95
Tubitak Marmara	Yes	Familiarisation is requested for the scientists arrived onboard. Meetings may be requested to get organised due to specific deck operations related with the cruise plan if necessary.
Marine Mobile Observation Platforms		
Baltic Gliders	No	
SOCIB Glider Facility	No	
AUV Barabas	Yes	VLIZ will provide specific familiarisation training to ensure users have a comprehensive understanding of the potential of marine robots and the used sensors, enabling them to effectively utilize these tools to fulfil their research objectives.
USV Adhemar	Yes	VLIZ will provide specific familiarisation training to ensure users have a comprehensive understanding of the potential of marine robots and the used sensors, enabling them to effectively utilize these tools to fulfil their research objectives.
Glider Yoko	Yes	We'll provide specific familiarisation training to ensure users have a comprehensive understanding of the potential of marine robots, empowering them to effectively utilize these tools to fulfil their research objectives.
ROV ARIANE	No	

Name of Infrastructure:	Are Infrastructure Users required to undertake any training prior to accessing your infrastructure?	If yes, please provide details:
UL-IROV	Yes	The access includes training of the system, expected output including working on navigational data and survey data streams. There is some preparation work such as integration and training included in the unit cost, this is done prior to operational days. The user can be onsite during operation or have access through a virtual component.
UL_MRE-ROV	Yes	The access includes training of the system, expected output including working on navigational data and survey data streams. There is some preparation work such as integration and training included in the unit cost, this is done prior to operational days. The user can be onsite during operation or have access through a virtual component.
SmartBay Glider	No	
Max Rover	No	
NorSOOP: Norwegian Ships of Opportunity Program	No	
SYKE Alg@line FerryBox Network	Yes	Simple instructions during the first visit. While visiting Ferry, users will always be accompanied by facility owner.
Fixed Marine Facilities		
SmartBay Observatory	No	
POSEIDON Observatory	No	
Western Mediterranean research facility (W1M3A)	No	

Name of Infrastructure:	Are Infrastructure Users required to undertake any training prior to accessing your infrastructure?	If yes, please provide details:
South Adriatic Sea E2M3A EMSO Regional Facility	Yes	Currently, Italian ships require a certificate of participation in the STCW95 course for boarding
Western Ionian Sea (WIS)	No	
SiCO	No	
CoCM	No	
SmartBay Buoy	No	
IMDBON (Irish Marine Data Buoy Observation Network)	No	
Utö Marine and Atmospheric Research Station	No	
Plocan Test Site	N/A	N/A
Experimental Research Facilities		
ISC-Lab	No	
Lehanagh Pool Marine Research Site	Yes	Sea survival training.
MI Newport Recirculating Aquaculture System	No	
EMBRC-Portugal-CIIMAR	Yes	Yes, internal training is required depending on the technological platform.

Name of Infrastructure:	Are Infrastructure Users required to undertake any training prior to accessing your infrastructure?	If yes, please provide details:
SYKE Mesocosm and Calibration Facility	Yes	Laboratory walk-through demonstration and safety instructions are given prior providing a permit to work in the facility
IMEV	No	
OOB	No	
SBR	No	
CCMAR	Yes	To work with animals, it is mandatory to have project approval in advance by the relevant authority and to be licensed to experiment with animals (vertebrates and cephalopods). Users receive an introduction to the infrastructure on arrival
River and Basin Supersites		
DANUBIUS-RI	No	
EMSO-EUXINUS	Yes	
iCIEM Ebro Delta Supersite	Yes	Specific workshops with users to facilitate the preparation of Transnational Access
Newport Catchment	Yes	Personal sea safety. Depending on what the research is, maybe fish tagging, use of anaesthesia, standard lab training. Basic training such as Lab Users Competency, Manual Handling, must be completed in advance.
Aircraft		
AIRS – Airborne Remote Sensing	Yes	CRM - Crew Resources Management
FLIS – Flying Laboratory of Imaging Systems	No	TA users are not expected onboard of the aircraft. The FLIS RI will acquire data from area specified by the TA user.

Name of Infrastructure:	Are Infrastructure Users required to undertake any training prior to accessing your infrastructure?	If yes, please provide details:
CWIS-II (AVIRIS-4)	Yes	
Drones		
UL Drone	Yes	General Operations training.
MAPEO	Yes	Training for quality assurance during drone data acquisition Training for Field software tool to upload the drone data
Satellite Services		
Terrascope	No	No